

Participant 15

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

team, people, software, agile, mistake, testing, communication, scenarios, quality, application, person, user, communicate, initiative, mobile application, mobile, knowledge, pair programming, problem, improve

SPEAKERS

Participant 15, Researcher

Researcher 00:00

Sorry, Participant 15, it was a little bit. It's the setup, but I think it's working now. So good morning again. Sorry about that. I'd like to thank you for doing the interview. And sorry about the little technical problems. I'd like to explain to you how the interview works, and we can start the interview. So basically, this is a research interview, and I'm interviewing people to try to understand how do they work in an Agile team? And basically, I'm focusing on how does it help when you admit mistakes when you bring up problems and you discuss them, etc. So the dynamic and the group, so I will be asking questions, and thanks for sending those answer online. upfront, and we will discuss some example from your own experience. Is that okay? Yep, perfectly fine. Okay. So we can start with a brief introduction, if you can introduce yourself briefly, what do you do and your experience and will continue after that?

Participant 15 01:16

Sure. So yeah, my name is Participant 15 and I'm a QA engineer at holding more than five years of experience in different organisations, I and I basically started my career in QA itself, but experience only and I allowed me to do in the personal and professional life because it's made a lot of flexibility in terms of adapting the changes in our daily routine, right. So I started my career as a QA engineer with a local company, so that in India for two than more than 2.5 years, and then I moved to Australia where I got a chance to lead the QA team for the company called [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] in which is located in Australia. For more than one year, I saw myself for that company, and I liked acuity and LM with an all metal and then I switched back into the full title answer. Okay, so I do have rich experience, and I live because I work for more than four years anything.

Researcher 02:19

Okay, great. Thank you. So what do you use in your team? Do you use Scrum,

Participant 15 02:27

Scrum and Kanban? Some time? It's depend on the organisation and requirement we have.

Researcher 02:32

Okay, can you briefly describe to me how do you use Scrum in your current team.

Participant 15 02:41

For Scrum we use two weeks of sprint, which will start from the sprint planning and all the teams together along with the development team product owner, the scrum master, all the team will get together and the product owner will explain the user stories, the business requirement with the whole team. And then in the refinement, will, like put all the stories together. And we will estimate estimated like according that, like when the city we have in the team. So it's basically we start start on the sprint planning. And once we have the clear requirement, we'll estimate them and pull into the two weeks of training. And once the like parliament will start along with like a will start their test preparation, because it's a process so we can, like lose simultaneously, like many things together, right? So it went from the development and when suggesting part is done, we'll deliver two weeks of sprint and products and it's like it's generally it we have the longer feature then we will not deliver we use the Canvas for the cortex we have the bigger requirement and cannot release the like smallest part in the production.

Researcher 03:58

Okay, thank you very much. What type of software do you develop in your team?

Participant 15 04:05

Currently, in my current project, we are working on the telecom domain. Like it's kind of. Like it's kind of a board of talent added to services where we have all the mobile and mobile devices and like internet connection, DTV, UTV, all kinds of stuff we are developing and will provide the service like we have the general store in the market, right? So user can go to the market store, and they can have that billing section, billing details or the device details, whatever they want to purchase or they wanted to update the parser it's in my current project. And like past product, I've worked I've worked for meditation apps, ecommerce websites and the small single rectangle looking at a lot of stuff out there.

Researcher 04:18

Okay, is this a new product or enhancing existing product?

Participant 15 04:25

New product.

Researcher 04:59

Okay, great. Thanks. To the discussion will be mainly around software quality. You know how software quality can be defined in many ways. But in this study, we opted for ISO definition. I'll read it to you and we can discuss it afterward. So the ISO definition of software quality state software quality is the degree to which the system satisfy the stated and implied needs of its various stakeholders and does provide value. This ISO model also cover some non functional characteristics, namely performance, compatibility, usability, reliability, security, merits and ability and possibility. Before we discuss this first, do you agree with this definition? Or Wouldn't you agree?

Participant 15 05:55

I've moved away in some cases, because I see that many application don't really much performance and security testing, because it's like a small application. And it's basically the upfront that then the user should be able to like, like, some people will, like develop the software for their personal use only, they don't want to make the use of with other people. So, they kind of were the application for their own business, they wanted to maintain their billing section or the NHS in the full one user only. So, security and performance testing should not be the issue for the such applications. But yeah, we if we are going for the bigger application, where we have the interaction with the user on the daily basis, and definitely we need to consider the best quality and the performance and security and nonconstant stuff as well.

Researcher 06:47

Okay, thanks for that. So, in your team, what type of quality assurance practices and processes we use to assure the software quality

Participant 15 06:59

I like we have multiple things in one project like non functional one automation one performance security of exploratory manual, like and different automation as well with the web and mobile. So, because we are working with like millions of users right. So, the security and the data protection is very important for for the company and business requirements. So, to maintaining the like security and performance we generally use performance and security testing, but it will be done with other teams, because they have a separate dedicated team that will continuously doing the performance and security stuff.

Researcher 07:41

Okay, great. We will move to the main questions. Before I do that, I will give you an assessment of your team from the question you answer and we will discuss it afterwards. So, from the answers you provided, I do believe that your team is relatively safe. What do you mean what do we mean by safe is your work environment your work environment welcomes admitting mistakes welcomes people bringing problem forwards and people feel at ease about talking about problem bringing initiatives discussion initiative, they feel confident and they have mutual respect toward each others. There is no fear from speaking up because there are no repercussions people feel at ease at speaking up about problems and issues. So, this is the type of teams I do believe you have would you agree?

Participant 15 09:09

Yeah, I totally agree. As I mentioned, like I worked with many different teams which are located in a different region of the world as well. So I what I see is that Agile is something that based on the adoption, whatever the mistake or the improvement we have on the place, we need to adopt it when we need to, like consider it. It is possible to implement in the stories, or we can make it in the backlog and we can like look together and where we have the chance to improve. We definitely need to go ahead for those improvements and suggestions.

Researcher 09:46

So in your opinion, what's made the team the way it is because this quality of safety, feeling comfortable about talking up, speaking up and what made it this way in your opinion.

Participant 15 10:01

I believe the communication is the key part in any team review or working on, if you're not doing communication, then you are looking at somewhere. Because whatever the problem we have in the plate, the one solution if you are not able to is communication, like because like the team will bring the different skill sets in one team, then only it will have the more like, perfect team for [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] So, if you're looking at somewhere, then definitely you need to communicate with the team and the standup or any other meetings. Right. Mainly, it's kind of a tradeoff and openness from everyone in the team. So if you're communicating then you have good kind of the confidence that you can speak up about any other issues or any suggestion or improvements later in the team.

Researcher 10:52

What is the size of the team? How long you have been working together?

Participant 15 10:55

Around 12. Don't forget you're ready. Okay, including development team and product owner, business analyst scrum master. This team, we worked together for more than 2 years.

Researcher 11:04

Okay, are you? Would you consider yourself a self organised team? Or there is some level of control over the team?

Participant 15 11:16

No, definitely we are, like, self-organized. Like, I never received any such thing that what you're doing right now, why you haven't done this thing? Because in Agile, I believe that you need to be like independent in some way that you are able to do some stuff independently without depending on any other person. So yeah, people were not pinging you at every time that why you haven't done this. Why? Because you're responsible for yourself and for your work on it. Our management trust we know what we doing and we can meet their expectations.

Researcher 11:50

Okay. Thanks for that. We will start with the questions I've sent you in the email and the answers. So the first one says, if you make mistakes on your team, it is often held against you. And your answer was No, I haven't seen such cases, when allows our team. If someone makes a mistake, there is nothing to point out to someone because in Azog, there is only one team, not an individual. So in this case, our team is going to take a look and try to avoid the same problem in the future. That's seems a very constructive and healthy way to approaching mistakes, isn't it?

Participant 15 12:43

Ah, no, because in Agile there is no individual there is only a team. So, if you are making a decision, then you need to consider as a team you don't make decisions alone, only because we like in sprint, like sprint ceremonies in agile ceremonies, you will have the feedback and you only need to consider it as a team. Because if there is one person is struggling at something, then we just need to ask them that we are here to help. It is not that this person is alone. We need to understand why they are

struggling in the first place. So we may need to consider that we need some training for this topic, because we see it as a chance for improvement for this topic to work on. And the same mistake we have or like we can learn from and avoid, because we have already the knowledge and the knowledge transfer session because we already observed this in the past and we have made improvements. So yeah, so pointing out mistakes is welcomed in my team and blame is not acceptable, but I definitely made the that is something that I haven't met yet. They can not properly follow agile and understand those. So could be the case. But in whatever I've seen for four years, and in my experience, I haven't seen that someone has pointed out to any illusion.

Researcher 13:58

So do you have an example to share with me where someone admitted a mistake? And how the team did deal with it?

Participant 15 14:09

And I can give my examples. When I joined when I joined the [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] in my past organisation, like I had not done any work in mobile testing, mobile app testing. But the major part was in September was a mobile application testing only. So yeah, I had expected web testing on me. But I joined the team because I have knowledge to learn and like excitement. So yeah, so after, like 15 to 20 days, I admitted that I haven't done any mobile testing yet. So I need some kind of training and some guidance so I can get into mobile testing as well. So yeah, they definitely agree with that part and I getting the like 15 Another trip and they had a good conversation with my colleagues and I learned mobile app testing and after 1.5 years, and they made the promotion, and then made a decision to, like, make me purely for all the web and mobile application testing teams. So yeah, if you are communicating and honest with the team, then you definitely have the solution. Hiding your problems, then you're going to suffer with your problem alone.

Researcher 15:24

Okay. So do you have an example where somebody brought up a mistake or error relating to quality? And how the team dealt with it?

Participant 15 15:36

Yeah, so yes, definitely, like, kind of thing. In past is a contact we had, like, we tested out that whole application in the lower amendment, but somehow some negative cases were, like, escalated to the production. So some, like some are, my colleague has noticed the mistake that they haven't encountered such scenario about the edge cases, but somehow they slipped into the production. So they came up that I have missed the scenario in the Delaware amendment, because it's edge cases, and it cannot be identified easily. So like people saying that it's okay, because we have a small impact on the application. And it's definitely that you are human, and we can make a mistake. So they definitely, like accepted the mistake of individual and we have fixed, like in the next sprint, because it's something that you have noticed and you can like not, you can communicate with the team, then looking at we have the solution.

Researcher 16:46

So do you think that this scenario has helped you in somehow as a team to, to improve to learn?

Participant 15 16:56

Yeah, yes, definitely. Because, like, if the same thing again, if you're making a mistake, then you should accept it. If someone has someone else has noticed, then that have the bad effect, if you haven't noticed this thing in the products and in the lower method as well. And if we have any bad impact on the production, then definitely someone will bring a point to you like that. Anyway, as someone has made the mistake, so they will point out that your team has had to encounter the scenario and we have the bad impact on the user because of decision.

Researcher 17:33

Okay, great. Thank you very much. I appreciate the example. We will move to the second question, which is member of your team can bring up problem and tough issues. Your answer was yes, all individuals in Agile team are free to bring any notice problem and tough issue which can help solve having communication with the team. Can you elaborate a little bit on that?

Participant 15 18:04

Yeah, so like in the team, we are, like all equal and no blame. So someone has faced any difficulty with the different part. So it's like, as I mentioned, in my previous experience, I have no mobile testing experience, like, it's gonna be tough for me to this mobile application properly, I can do that right. But in a not in a proper way that I can be have the 100% confident that we can release a song when in the production in the mobile application itself. So it was an easy part for some other person because they have already done that part, but not for me in any initial time. Right. So the toughest issue can be the easiest issue for someone else. But if you're bringing it to the team level, then we definitely have the solution where people like people can do the pair programming and they can like teach and think together and improve together the process and solve the problem.

Researcher 19:05

So, can you share with me an example where somebody or yourself brought a problem? That was your observing the team and how did you go about it and how did the team dealt with it?

Participant 15 19:20

Yeah, so, what I like in my previous team in India, like people, like one of my colleagues was not able to do it, like congregation because in India, people will rarely last people can speak in English. But yeah, that is true. So, yeah, so people don't but we are working in the international team. So definitely the English is the key to having the communication right. So what we are doing is that I was sitting next to him when he wants to when he wanted to explain the issue to somebody else. So I was reading that or guiding him to explain the issue where he needed. I also can be right. And I like to the communication, but I wanted to, like, teach him that how we can do and what improvements where we can turn in the sentences and the explanation. So it was the best part for him. But yeah, we're able to, like make some, like 20% to 30% improvement within the 10 days.

Researcher 20:21

That's great. That was nice of you. Do you have another example where the problem was related to software quality?

Participant 15 20:33

Like, software qualities. Okay. Yeah. So when I was initially, in my team, like I had, like, I was working in the order module, like the billing section and all that stuff. But like, when the new journey will come, they were they were not able to, like, work on the order? Well, because it was a very tough part two, because it will directly impact on the business and business users, right. So what we were doing is like, when their health and energy is on the order module, they will come with me that I was explaining the stuff or like what business use business scenarios, enter test intervals, we can test on this user stories they want or they don't have much, maybe they don't have much knowledge and initial level. So, I had a bit of experience in those modules. So I was exploring and I was telling that these scenarios can be done, this edge cases can be done, this negative testing can be done this positive testing can be done I was like explaining the scenarios there was equity doing and we're able to make the software opposite as much as possible, because I cannot help him to do the whole thing because like, that is their job, but I was helping him out to make the better software in terms of any story.

Researcher 21:54

So, in what shape or how did this initiative of you helping helps the final quality of the software?

Participant 15 22:05

Ah, that is a good thing. That is a good question. Because like as I mentioned, that is the has a user story, the story is written a nice way of business scenarios right. But the thing is thing was that they were able to test things only which are written in the user stories itself, but they don't want like they cannot think the other business scenario which can be affected to the another module, because in the like, if we had order module, then it will going to show in the report itself, they are going to send the messages and emails to the like the actual users right. So, if we are able to identify the other business scenarios and use cases to make the test coverage end to end, which can be impacted to the another module, then it will be very helpful for them to identify the issues like I made the order, but the email was not sent out, but it was not mentioned in the business user stories that we need to send the email out or that it should not be impacted to any other module right. So, if we encounter such things in like it will link with another module then it will help to make the software robust and not to break easily.

Researcher 23:17

Okay, fantastic. Thank you, we will move to the next question, which was people on your team sometimes reject other further ideas, you said now in the Agile ceremonies, everyone can present their own ideas and whichever is the best suitable for the team to improve the productivity of the Practice activity and any other improvement can be done with those ideas. There is nothing such a case where people will reject your idea. So can you take me too when somebody brings an idea to the team how the team react, how it goes about it? Yeah.

Participant 15 24:00

Yeah. So, what we like I have to have experience examples into development and testing. So, when I when we like any incident where there was knotting here, so we wanted to like build proper cured in the fall processes. So because there was no proper process in the testing. So, what we made is we like take some solution from the whole the QA that what processes and more like tools and technology we

can use to make better processes, right. So people come up with different tools and different ideas and different technologies like Scrum and Agile or Kanban or waterfall whatever the methodology we wanted to bring as part of our teams right? So people can bring their ideas in a nice and such a way that that explain the business themes for Okay, so whatever the past is suitable. And so we took all together. And we made the decision to keep one process in alignment.

Researcher 25:12

Okay, thanks for that example. How is how that initiative or sharing the idea with the team and implementing it has had software quality?

Participant 15 25:26

Ah, yeah. So if you're working in small team and smaller projects, and we definitely don't want to do Scrum and Agile processes, because I could have a longer process and other methodology because we, if we have a smaller small application, then we can directly bring the issues and developer can solve the issues easily. But what did they think that we need to go to the on the process because we want to create a user's defect, and the developer wants to like, evaluate the effort for them. And then we'll go to the next sprint, because we don't want to, like disturb our current sprint, because you already helped pull some user story in your sprint right? So it will like for bigger application, we definitely, like easy for us to implement earlier process, but not for the small application and a short week of spring.

Researcher 26:24

Thanks for that. I just want to follow up on something. So far in your answers, I understand that you praise a lot agile for helping the team the way it is. Is it only as at helping you to work the way you are now and bring this feeling of safety? Or do you think that the team, the individual, the management also helping?

Participant 15 26:54

Yeah. All together help us out. Right now I am. It's not as I'll say something. But I do actually that I love agile very much. Because as I mentioned that it will help me out to all of the changes very quickly, and to make central changes in a quick manner way. Right. So that is why I praise it a lot. And I like the approach very much.

Researcher 27:20

What do you like about it?

Participant 15 27:23

Repeat please?

Researcher 27:26

And in what way as I'll helps quality in your opinion?

Participant 15 27:32

Yes. Like, as I mentioned that if we have any issues on the place, and people can talk together, and we can definitely can pull that down, pull that out, and we can solve quickly as much as possible. It is not

something that we need to wait for some time that no I do. I'm doing this. I can't do this right now. It is not scalable.

Researcher 27:53

And so yeah, so the communication and the collaboration helps, right? Yeah, yeah. Okay, well, we will move to the next example with about initiatives. I think you already shared an example about bringing ideas in the ceremonies. So the question was, it is safe to take initiative in your team? And you said absolutely, yes. taking initiative on your team will increase the value of an individual and you can improve the relationship within the team. With your initiative, you might solve bigger problem on the team, which could be outstanding for everyone. I strongly recommend taking initiative whenever you want, whenever you feel to do so. There are two parts to your answer. I'd like you to explain the first part, and I'll ask one question about the second part. So the first part you said taking initiative and improved relationships within the team. Can you explain a little bit that?

Participant 15 29:08

Sorry, was lacking?

Researcher 29:10

Yes. Sorry. You said you said can you help me better? Yeah, sorry. You said that taking initiative helps improving relations in the team. Can you explain a little bit more?

Participant 15 29:26

Yes. So, when someone will take the initiative, they will different endpoint to do collaboration and communication with the team right. So, like when someone will share their ideas and people will try to take the interest in in a person that this person can bring initiatives. Initiatives do some great things we have observed in our team. So yeah, people make some more interesting new and it will like have the better communication and collaboration with the person so it will definitely going to bring a lot of value in your relationship or relation with the other person. When people bring initiatives, eventually everything improves over time, processes, relationship in the team and the quality of our software.

Researcher 30:01

So what you say and when people bring initiative others appreciate? And that's yeah. Do you have an example to share with me when somebody brought an initiative and the relationship has improved?

Participant 15 30:16

Yes. So I, I do have my example. Yeah. So we were testing application where we wanted to, like, test the application in different languages and the location, but as a person, we cannot go into a different location, and we can't speak and understand the whole languages, right. So I like to approach the management, like to do a testing in a different location. And the closer we can speak and with that native languages, so what we do is we bring Liqui Hi, lagoon was helping out us to find such candidates, candidates in the local region, and the local person who can test the application for 30 to 50 minute. And they can, like, do, like they can suggest is that what works and the second is we can improve.

Researcher 31:16

So those are social in nature, these gestures that are social in nature, you help each other outside the software developments. Yeah, that makes sense. Yeah, that's interesting. The second part is with your initiative, you must solve bigger problems. That's interesting. So, do you have an example with somebody? Do you have an example where somebody brought an initiative and it solved a problem?

Participant 15 31:50

Yeah, in the same, in the same example, I can see that we have like a lot of negative reviews in application that the sponsor translation is not correct as for like languages, because if I'm using any application that I want, that this person can understand our local language and they can have the better like, they have made a lot of attentions for us in our region. So, like, Victor and like, what we did is like we hired a local person, we did some improvement, the quality assurance that we have bigger like we can have a better transcript language translation in the local languages and what they need that also we can identify because it's in a different region, they want something else, because not every person and every region has the same interest in in the market, right? So what we did is we hired a person will bring a lot of value in quality assurance with that part, and people were like, we get a lot of positive reviews that you have made them to match. So in that way, we made a bigger impact on the users.

Researcher 33:07

Okay, great. Thanks a lot for that example. Do you have another example where somebody brought an initiative related to software quality and how it did help

Participant 15 33:26

I guess in quality assurance, I guess like as I mentioned that if we are like, we don't have a we if someone has no period a right and before doing the quality assurance is a different team. Like there is of course as a user like the one QA engineer can be assigned to the particular team and another curious and different particular game, but there is no centralised acuity right. So, so, someone else cannot be there with the knowledgeable without the other team, but if we have the central care processes, then all the person can align with all the different teams and they can have the knowledge. So, if someone is not available at some time, because they can be like resigned, they can be sick and they cannot be able to go for some time. So, in that way, if we have the knowledge of another person, then they can have the like they can bring the value to the another team as well. And in that way, we cannot be like be ideal for one day. Like kill the another person is available for us.

Researcher 34:37

Okay, fantastic. Thank you very much. I appreciate those examples. I'll move to the next question. Which was, it is difficult to ask other members of your team to help and you say no, not at all. Asking for other members for help will be in the relationship to pills, and can have great bones and communications, we have their programming in Agile with which represent where more than one person brings together. And you work on the same problem at the same time and you share the knowledge. So asking others, it's much easier if you are in the agile approach. That's very interesting. The first thing is I've noticed what makes people wanting to help each other.

Participant 15 35:40

Because they bring a different skill set in, in in the team, right? So we are doing right now like we're currently doing a pair programming where we have two sessions in a day, where we can bring one user story or one defect in, in a pair programming by two or more people will bring a friend to the meeting, and they can like code and do the business resolution in one meeting. So what we did is someone has a different stakes and someone like if we want to build any software, then we need our front end engineer, back end engineer, or sometimes business analyst as well. So we cannot, like do the individual communication with a different person. So what we can do is like we can like three person can bring together and in one meeting we can do one go solution. In that way,

Researcher 36:38

Yeah, yeah, continue.

Participant 15 36:41

In that way, we can have the better collaboration and the communication in one step. And if we have any issues, we can directly communicate and without having any hesitation.

Researcher 36:52

Fantastic. So you mentioned that you use programming to share knowledge and to help each other. When do you use pair programming? And how does it help?

Participant 15 37:08

Yeah, so what we are doing right now are like, like something I have a mobile application testing knowledge, and someone wants, like someone is from the web testing knowledge, web testing, knowledge. So, the product is going to be a same for our web and mobile application. So what we are doing that we check the integration within our mobile application in the web application, if we are sharing any link like if there is any course or something meditation or any social data. So we are selling, we are copying a link, we are checking, checking in the mobile application, then tapping on the link will bring the mobile application open and see the scope of expected thing. And the same thing, we are going to check in the mobile it like web application, right? So what we are doing is right we are doing the billing integration with the mobile and the web application. So what it will do is it will like visually, it will have in fact that it will work in both way. So we don't need to be like SEO that people using on the web and puppet who doesn't have a mobile application.

Researcher 38:17

So do you use pair programming between to share knowledge? Okay, that's great. So in this example, you shared knowledge and you bring your knowledge from one idea to another, how does it help improve in software quality?

Participant 15 38:39

I could improve that. Like, we had a lot of issues in the past that some links are not working in the web. And some links are not working in the end a mobile application, because like, if I copied any link in a mobile from the mobile application, and if I'm using the same links to the another mobile is mobile, then

it will working fine. Right, it will work fine. But if I'm using the same link to a different browser, then it won't work. So what we are doing is we can check the such scenarios together with a different person. And we can have the rubber software that that cannot use us like fee ideas for use the software in a different browser and the different devices.

Researcher 39:27

So this note is helps you to improve your testing capability. And by doing that the software quality improves. That's how I understand from this example. Yeah. Thank you. That was a good example. I'll move to the next question. So it says no one on my team would deliberately act in a way that undermines my effort. If your answer was yes, I agree everyone is given the best with the unique scale. So everybody or everyone is going to notice the effort every individual has has made within the team. So someone is not, would deliberately act in a way to undermine anybody's efforts. In fact, the team will encourage to do more effort like it. So in your opinion, what makes people wanting to invest more effort

Participant 15 40:36

Because, like, what I believe is that if I'm doing such things in a greater way, and people will encourage you to do such things, because you're doing such a good thing, so definitely, in the end, it is a team effort, right? So definitely, it's going to be for the team and the rewards are for your team as well. So within the teams, if you're being a good team member, we'll try to encourage you to do such a good thing because everybody is making an effort to do their best.

Researcher 41:11

Do you think it helps quality it helps to improve the software quality when people support each other?

Participant 15 41:19

It definitely does because like there are multiple scenarios can be there. We improve the knowledge within the team. So we teach each others how to deliver a better quality in better and improved ways. So at times we are going to deliver a better quality. Because we help each others the best ways to achieve quality.

Researcher 41:59

Okay, fantastic. Thanks for that. I think we come up to the last question, we'll discuss it and we will conclude the interview. So the last question I've sent it says working with members of my teams, my unique skills and talents are valuable and utilise, you said yes, definitely everyone bring unique skills and the other team and everyone should be valued and utilise the best to make work done. At the end it will be considered as a teamwork only. Can you elaborate and add a little bit to this.

Participant 15 42:41

So yeah, so when you are going to join a new team, there will be a new stick that will be a new product that will be a new domain. So what people will do is like a data centre and all business knowledge with you, once you are comfortable with that part and the thing that you are doing, they will try to upgrade you in a different way. Like I was doing a functional testing and the manual testing for the six month like but now I do have a knowledge and do manual testing and the product. So they are encouraging me to

do automation. Superb, so we can like our derivative work. So right now I'm doing automation. So they will encourage you to do such small things that will bring the more value in or less time.

Researcher 43:31

Thank you. That's very, that's it seems like it's a very positive energy and you work in a very constructive and positive environment. People encourage each other. Yes. Sorry.

Participant 15 43:49

I'm always trying to be a positive. And

Researcher 43:52

Yeah, so you achieved a very good atmosphere to work together with well done. So what advice would you give to somebody who wants to adopt Agile to reach this level of safety and collaboration you have in your team?

Participant 15 44:15

Yeah, so there are four Agile Manifesto. You already know that right? Yeah. Yeah. So what is my third is communication collaboration or the comprehensive documentation.

Researcher 44:29

So how can I get to that level communication and collaboration because not everybody? Yes, sorry. Yes.

Participant 15 44:38

So attending anything in the team just try to communicate try to like make it fixed and resolved as soon as possible as a team not you don't need to be I will go a stick that I cannot communicate with my junior my senior that what they will think about me what, what one thing that addresses aggression. And I will have after this thing, because people mindset, whatever the people, people want my anything if you are communicated with them and accept your mistakes. What they will do is they're trying to make you in a way that you, you don't want to do it hundreds and 1000s of mistakes, but the one rule is that you can't do repetitive mistakes.

Researcher 45:27

How do you how do you try not to replicate mistakes?

Participant 15 45:33

I tried to bring the solution. I am like I'm trying to like not to do the same thing I did in the past which, like, ended up with a mistake.

Researcher 45:49

So as a team, you do do the same the whole team try not to repeat mistakes let you do you think because the mistakes are communicated and admitted?

Researcher 46:13

Okay, yeah, yeah. Great. I don't have more questions. Do you have any things you'd like to add in this topic? I haven't covered the my question.

Participant 15 46:27

I was just curious that what you're going to do, after like taking so many interviews with the actual person,

Researcher 46:36

Yes, what we do is we analyse the interviews, we do have some technique, our own way of doing it. And we draw conclusions. And we propose findings from the study. And we write it in a scientific or academic paper and we publish it or we try to publish it. That's what happens. Yeah. So like the question I asked, how would you advise an Agile team to get where you got? So that's the purpose of the research, we talk to people like yourself with good experiences. And we try to draw some conclusion how teams managed to achieve this level of safety that you have in your own teams. And we communicate that and we communicate the impacts and effects of having such a safe work environment, and how does it help? So and we write research paper and we publish them. If you're interested. Once I have a draft, I can share it with you, if you like Yeah, sure. Okay, guys, any other questions or comments?

Participant 15 47:51

No, I like I tend to use it. We had a good conversation, because I'm really looking forward.

Researcher 47:58

Yeah. Thank you. It was very, very insightful. Thank you very much, and we'll stay in touch. Okay. Thank you. Have a good day. Bye. Thanks for your time. I appreciate bye. Yeah, same Yeah.